

Some application of random fuzzy queueing system based on fuzzy simulation

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Abstract : This paper studies a random fuzzy queueing system that the interarrival times of customers arriving at the server and the service times are independent and identically distributed random fuzzy variables. We match the random fuzzy queueing system with the random fuzzy alternating renewal process and we do not use from α -pessimistic and α -optimistic values to estimate the average chance of the event "random fuzzy queueing system is busy at time t", we employ the fuzzy simulation method in practical applications. Some theorem is proved and finally we solve a numerical example with fuzzy simulation method.

Keywords : Random fuzzy variables, Fuzzy simulation method, Queueing system, Interarrival times.

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